

Multiscale GWR needs looking at: searching, looking for LOVE (low optimal value evaluations)

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Summary

GWR is a commonly used technique for understanding process spatial heterogeneity. Recently Multi-Scale GWR (MS-GWR) has been proposed as the default GWR as it allows the scale of individual response-to-predictor relationships to vary spatially, rather than a “best on average” scale with standard GWR. This work describes problems with the back-fitting algorithms used to search through the solution-space used in *all* MS-GWR implementations. It compares the results of these with a linear search and shows current MS-GWR searches to be sub-optimal. `gwverse` proposes a new modular structure for GWR that incorporates a function factory approach. A number of areas of future work are described in order to create a new MS-GWR module in `gwverse`.

KEYWORDS: GWR, Multiscale GWR, Search Heuristics;

1. Introduction

GWR (Brunsdon et al., 1996) investigates spatial variation in relationships between response and predictor variables. Its outputs include spatially distributed coefficient estimates which allow the investigation of process spatial heterogeneity, and thereby deeper process understanding. The geographically weighted (GW) framework – in which a series of local models are constructed from weighted data subsets defined by a moving window or kernel – is increasingly used to explore spatial variation in model parameters or components. Examples include GW-PCA (Harris et al 2015) GW-Discriminant Analysis (GW-DA) (Brunsdon et al 2007) and GW correspondence matrices (Comber et al 2017). The critical step in a GW analysis is to determine the kernel size or bandwidth as this drives the scale of aggregation or smoothing in the outputs. There are methods for determining bandwidth by optimising some measure of model fit.

Standard GWR identifies a single bandwidth under the assumption that the relationships between the response and predictor variables operate at the same spatial scale. However, this is frequently not the case as some predictor-to-response relationships can operate at larger scales and others at smaller ones. A standard GWR nullifies these differences and finds a ‘best-on-average’ single bandwidth to describe scale of relationship non-stationarity (geographical variation). To address this one of the key GWR developments has been the extension to Multi-Scale GWR (MS-GWR) (Yang 2014; Fotheringham et al 2017). In this, the bandwidth for each relationship is determined separately, allowing the scale of individual response-to-predictor relationships to vary. Indeed MS-GWR is now recommended as the default GWR (Comber et al 2022), with a standard GWR only being appropriate in very specific circumstances. Comber et al (2022) provide a route map to determine the correct choice of GWR model. This shift to MS-GWR as the default GWR has potential implications for other GW models and thinking around them. For example, it suggests that multi-scale discriminant analysis (MS-LDA) as proposed by Comber et al (2021) should be the default GW-DA.

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As with standard GWR, the determination of optimal parameter-specific bandwidths through some measure of model fit is the critical step in a MS-GWR analysis. However, recent work has shown that the back-fitting approach used by *all* implementations of MS-GWR (standalone, Python, R, etc) to determine the individual bandwidths per variable generates sub-optimal results (Comber et al 2021). This paper exemplifies this problem and suggests a number of areas of research that could be undertaken to address this problem.

2. The problem

All current approaches to bandwidth selection in MS-GWR (standalone implementations, Python packages, R packages) use a back-fitting algorithm based on that used in early implementations of the Generalised Additive Model (GAM) (Hastie and Tibshirani, 1987). What this does in overview, is determine the bandwidths for each parameter one at a time, passing smoothing functions that assume error terms are known from one stage to the next. This approach is pragmatic as the search spaces are huge (examples below) but it is logically flawed as it does not evaluate *all possible combinations* of bandwidths, and therefore risks missing important variable interactions and structure in the spatial data.

Consider the following example: a dataset with 5000 observations and 9 predictor variables (plus the Intercept) requires 9.8×10^{36} bandwidth combinations to be evaluated to identify the optimal adaptive bandwidths for each input variable plus the intercept. Current approaches for searching through this highly dimensional solution space are pragmatic but sub-optimal. The back-fitting approach in a MS-GWR, determines the bandwidth for each predictor variable one at a time, reducing the search space in the example above to 5×10^5 possible solutions.

3. Example and results

The data in Figure 1 is the well-known dataset for Georgia in the USA, containing 159 counties and some socio-economic data. The aim here is to construct a very simple MS-GWR model of Median Income using 2 covariates, the percentage of the population with degrees (*% Degrees*) as an indicator of earnings potential and the percentage of elderly people (*% Elderly*) as an indicator of poverty due to the lack of a state pension. Thus, the search space is relatively small, comprised of 4×10^6 combinations of adaptive MS-GWR bandwidths to evaluate.

Figure 1 The Georgia data and the Median Income variable for the counties of Georgia.

First, for comparison an adaptive bandwidth GWR model can be optimally determined using an AICc evaluation of model fit through a linear search of bandwidths. This indicates an adaptive bandwidth of the nearest 48 data points to be included in each local regression. Next, adaptive bandwidth optimisation can be undertaken using the GWmodel R package for MS-GWR, using the back-fitting approach. This indicates optimal bandwidths of 34 data points for the Intercept (highly local), 157 for % Degree (global) and 31 for % Elderly (highly local). Finally, a linear search through the adaptive bandwidth space indicates the best performing combinations of bandwidths to be 76 for the Intercept (moderately local), 44 for % Degree (highly local) and 20 for % Elderly (highly local). These results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 GWR and MS-GWR Bandwidths

Variable	GWR Standard	MS-GWR Back-fitting	MS-GWR Linear Search
Intercept	48	34	76
% Degree	48	157	44
% Elderly	48	31	20

The behaviour of the GWR model fit with scale (through bandwidth) is shown in Figure 2 along with the summaries of the MS-GWR fits from a linear search for the different covariates. The full 4-dimensional space comprising the Intercept, % Degree, % Elderly and AICc fit score, cannot be visualised. So, Figure 2 shows the median model fit scores (AICc) summarised for each bandwidth (actually a sample of bandwidths for visual clarity), for each model, with the error bars indicating the interquartile range of fit scores at that bandwidth. Whilst the standard GWR, model fits behave in a nested and hierarchical way, descending to a minima at 48 observation points, the divergence between the optimal bandwidths for the MS-GWR by linear search in Table 1 and the “trends” in Figure 2 indicate the difficulty in adopting search heuristics in MS-GWR bandwidth searches, and the potential origins of the sub-optimal solutions identified through the back-fitting approach.

Figure 2 Fit scores for standard GWR and median fit scores for MS-GWR by linear search for each bandwidth (the inter-quartile range of the fit scores are indicated by the error bars for the MS-GWR bandwidths).

4. Discussion

The search algorithms used in many spatial models have a number of assumptions embedded within them. The most important of these is that there is some process convergence across scales: as scales of analysis increase or decrease, for example as with a kernel bandwidth, then the process of interest behaves in a hierarchical and predictable way, increasing or decreasing with scale, such as is evident in Figure 2 for a standard GWR. For these problems, well known and commonly used heuristics like the Golden Search can be used to find some inflection point indicating an optimal fit. For a single bandwidth, in a standard GWR this assumption usually holds, with only a minor danger of search heuristics getting caught in local minima (see Figure 2). However, with MS-GWR convergence cannot be assumed in the same way. This is also clearly evident in Figure 2. In fact, any hierarchical and nested trends in the AICc scores for the MS-GWR bandwidths are difficult to discern and predict. This is because of the multivariate interactions that occur when different individual parameter-specific bandwidths are used.

These issues will be addressed in future work, particularly to overcome the tension between the need for search heuristics (efficiency) and brute force linear searches (comprehensiveness). This tension arises because of the highly dimensional nature of MS-GWR bandwidth fitting and the many irregular local minima in this search space, that need to be quantified to ensure optimality.

A new structure has been proposed for GW models called the *gwverse*. This has at its core 2 key ideas: a modular composition and the incorporation of a function factory approach. These are described in Comber et al (2021b) and a simple R package with 2 modules has been constructed that is able to undertake standard GWR. Ongoing work is in the process of expanding the functionality of *gwverse* to incorporate a MS-GWR module. The critical issue in this is to identify appropriate methods with which to move through highly dimensional search spaces. Possible solutions include elegantly coded (eg including bridges to other programming languages) brute force with efficient linear searches, or by matching the characteristics of different search heuristics (and the assumptions they contain) to the characteristics of the specific spatial dataset being analysed.

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Biographies

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